

THE IMPACT OF ACTIVATING BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE VIA PRE-LISTENING ACTIVITIES ON NON-ENGLISH MAJORS' LISTENING COMPREHENSION AT HO CHI MINH CITY OPEN UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

Although English take a dominant role as the first foreign language in Vietnam, the teaching of this subject has not been properly focused with respect to all four language skills, especially listening comprehension. The teacher's listening instruction still confuses learners at tertiary level because of the problems related to making use of students' background knowledge. Therefore, this experimental research aims at exploring the effectiveness of using pre-listening activities to activate students' background knowledge on listening comprehension. The participants were 61 non-English majors from the control class (CG) and the experimental class (EG) at Ho Chi Minh City Open University. The instruments for data collection consisted of pre- and post-tests and pre- and post-questionnaire. The findings of the study confirmed the positive effects of pre-listening activities on students' listening comprehension ability and on their attitudes towards the experimental teaching. Based on the research outcomes, some implications were offered for the teaching of listening comprehension.

Key words: Background knowledge, activate, pre-listening activities, listening comprehension

1 INTRODUCTION

In reality, the teaching and learning of listening to non- English major classes at universities in Vietnam is not taken into much consideration and even ignored. On their part, teachers usually confuse their students in listening classes, requiring them to listen word by word and/or to translate the listening text into Vietnamese, and this causes about 63% of them to be able neither to catch the gist of the listening nor to pick up necessary details (Ton, 2009, p. 2). Moreover, they ask them to listen without any provision of the context based on which they can guess the upcoming information. Consequently, they make them tired of and bored with listening time. On their part, 70% of students lack knowledge of language, culture and other kinds of background knowledge. Due to this problem, they are hardly able to predict what is going to be spoken, or infer what they have just heard. They even misunderstand the message first spoken (Ton, 2003, p. 3). Therefore, both teachers and learners are involved in such a constraint. However, teachers are those who can be responsible for finding the solutions.

Until the most recent years, as investigated in Do (2015), the teaching and learning listening at Hanoi University of Industry encounter a lot of difficulties, and the problem exists owing to students' low listening competence, students' limited vocabulary and students' poor background knowledge.

To search for a solution for such a problem, in recent years, there have been several studies in this field implemented in Vietnamese educational context. However, they all focused on effectiveness of pre-listening instructions in general, not on that of background knowledge activating activities in particular. For example, the findings by Tran (2010) indicate that pre-listening activities as predicting, discussing, brainstorming, and questioning were highly appreciated by the students, and these activities were believed to generate interest and confidence, create input for listening, and change their role to become active listeners. And Luu, and Vo (2014) carry out a research related to listening performance and schema construction activities for non-English major students; the findings from posttests show that there is no differences between the control group and the experiment group.

Therefore, the present study aims at exploring the effectiveness of activities to activate students' background knowledge at pre-listening stage on listening comprehension. To achieve this purpose, the research addresses one main research question below:

What are the educational values of activating students' background knowledge via pre-listening activities in teaching them listening comprehension in a language classroom?

As this question entails two aspects of comprehension ability and attitudes, it is necessary to find the answers to the following two sub-questions:

1.1 To what extent does the activation of students' background knowledge via pre-listening activities help them improve their listening comprehension?

1.2 What are the students' attitudes towards these activities?

Although the problem studied is not new for many language researchers, the difference lies in the reality of teaching. The research is conducted in the hope to encourage teachers of general English at universities to apply the trialed program into English listening teaching situations of their own.

2 BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE AND LANGUAGE COMPREHENSION

Theory in relation to background knowledge and language comprehension restricted to listening comprehension of this study will be presented in the following subsections

2.1 Defining background knowledge

Background knowledge is sometimes technically called *schemata* (plural form of schema). As found in Strangman and Meyer (2003, p. 2), the terms background knowledge and *prior knowledge* can be used interchangeably, and they are specialized in many more specific dimensions or forms such as *conceptual knowledge*, *subject-matter knowledge*, *strategic knowledge*, and *personal knowledge*. In Dam, Engberg and Arborgast's (2005, p. 2), *world*

knowledge, encyclopedic knowledge, and extra- or non-linguistic knowledge are also used to refer to background knowledge. Especially, Steven (1980, p. 151) offered us a rather simple definition that background knowledge is what a person already knows about subject.

2.2 Background knowledge and language comprehension

The current theoretical approaches related to language comprehension activities emphasize the role of individuals' background knowledge as part of cognitive context (Barcelona, Benczes, & Ibanez, 2011, p. 257). Gonzalez-Marquez (2007, p. 411) offers one important idea, coming from cognitive linguistics, that words (and other sorts of linguistic structures) are not intrinsically meaningful, but are used by speakers to actively construct meaning. This author adds that text, any text either spoken or written, does not itself carry meaning but only provides directions for listeners. This author also shows that understanding the meaning of many words requires an understanding of the concepts and conventions surrounding their use. For example, "weekend" presumes an understanding of the structure of the week that many people in industrialized countries work from Monday to Friday, but not on Saturday and Sunday (Fillmore, 1968, as cited in Gonzalez-Marquez 2007, p. 411). This view is an explanation of why the ability in interpretation and inference is needed for comprehension.

2.3 Typology of background knowledge

2.3.1 Background knowledge of language

Generally, background knowledge of language, as pointed out by Carrell and Eisterhold (1983, as cited in Singhal, 1998, p. 7), refers to the reader's existing language proficiency in pronunciation, vocabulary, grammar, and idioms, and so on. In this view, thanks to repeated examples, first language (L1) user may be able to generalize a pattern or to guess meaning of a word, which is not part of his/her linguistic knowledge in his/her mind. In the same way, new knowledge of language is built up to help second language (L2) learners. As a result, the more this knowledge they possess, the faster they acquire information and the better understanding they can get (Carrell, 1984, as cited in Li, Wu & Wang, 2007, pp. 18-19).

2.3.2 Background knowledge of content

As reported by Carrell (1984, as cited in Li, Wu & Wang, 2007, p. 19), background knowledge of content refers to one's stored knowledge in relation to the content area of a text or its topic of a text; it consists of topic familiarity, cultural knowledge and previous experience with the field or the content domain of a text. That is this type of knowledge includes all of the prior knowledge or experience related to cultures, peoples, habits, subject matters one is majoring in, and even information related to the topic present in a text.

2.4 Strategies to activate background knowledge

According to Cook (1989, p. 69), the mind stimulated by key words or phrases in the text or by context activates background knowledge; it is not a conscious process but automatic cognitive responses. This author clarifies that such knowledge in mind is activated in two ways. First,

thanks to retrieval or remembering, new information from the outside world can be cognitively received and related to already known information stored in memory, so this is also called recalling or remembering process. Through this way, new concepts are assimilated into existing schemata, making our background knowledge altered or expanded. Second, in case, already existing background knowledge is absent, the process of building up new background knowledge occurs. New information can be represented by new mental structures. In a word, background knowledge is activated in two ways of recalling existing knowledge, and providing new knowledge.

2.5 The role of teacher in activating background knowledge

While the background knowledge students bring with them helps them perform a listening task more successfully, their teachers should make certain preparation for them to do so (Othman & Vanathas, 2005, p. 31). The important task, as suggested by Cooper, Kiger and Au (2009, p. 85), is that teachers have to decide what prior knowledge should be probably reminded of or/and developed for a particular material and teaching context. Especially, teachers have to design pre-listening activities to activate students' background knowledge while teaching listening.

As suggested in Doff (1988); Underwood (1989); (Alexander & McCune, 2007); Ur (1984), the activities of previewing, questioning, brainstorming can be used for recalling background knowledge, and the ones of pre-teaching vocabulary can be used for building up background knowledge.

3 METHODS

The research is conducted at Ho Chi Minh City Open University on non-English major classes. In the experiment, the students of controlled group (CG) were taught by strictly following the activities of listening section available in Hemispheres book 1, while the students of experiment group (EG) were taught with pre-listening activities activating students' background knowledge.

The research was carried out employing two data collection methods: tests, questionnaires to examine the effects of experimental or independent variable (pre-listening activities) on dependent variable (listening comprehension) of this study.

The pre-test and post-test of this research were established by the researcher herself. In addition, while designing the post-test, she carefully checked the clearness of the test directions, the appropriateness of the test items, the level of difficulty of vocabulary and syntax, the topic familiarity of the listening materials. Specially, ten post-test copies were piloted on two groups of 10 students of the Controlled Group (CG) before delivering to all of the Experiment Group (EG) and CG students.

Pre and post-questionnaires in this research were set with the mixture of closed and open questions to explore the EG students' reflections on the researcher's new teaching method. To make sure that the students understood the concepts in each question and her intentions, five copies had been piloted on five students of the CG before a copy was delivered to all the EG students.

4 DATA INTERPRETATION AND FINDINGS

The analysis and interpretation will be organized into two main sections in accordance with two sub research questions of this study. There were 24/32 students of the CG and 26/29 students of the EG doing pre-test, and there were only 18/32 students of the CG and 17/29 students of the EG doing both pre- and post-tests. Accordingly, the following data analysis of tests will rely on the results obtained in such situations.

4.1 Students' listening comprehension ability

4.1.1 Comparison of the values on pre-test scores contributed by two groups

Table 1: Descriptive values on pre-test scores of the two groups

Group Statistics – Post-test Scores							
Group	N	Mm	Max	Mean	Mode	Median	SD
CG	24	4.0	9.0	6.16	6.5	6.0	1.4
EG	26	4.0	8.0	6.00	6.0	6.0	1.1

When looking at Table 1, we can see that there is a difference in means between the CG (6.16) and the EG (6.0). To confirm if they are really different, an independent samples *t*-test drawn from these statistical descriptions was run. The result of *t*-test calculation shows that the level of significance at 0.15 is much bigger than 0.05. Inferentially, the null hypothesis that the two groups had the same ability in English listening comprehension before the treatment was supported. Therefore, the researcher could confidently apply the treatment on any of the two selected classes, and she, in fact, decided to do the experiment on those students who had the mean score of 6.0. And right below is the provision of the post-test results

4.1.2 Comparison of the values on post-test scores achieved by two groups

Table 2: Descriptive values on post-test scores of the two groups

Group Statistics - Post-test Scores							
Group	N	Mm	Max	Mean	Mode	Median	SD
CG	18	4.0	9.0	6.9	7.0/8.5	7.0	.70
EG	17	6.0	9.0	7.8	8.0	8.0	1.5

As displayed in Table 2, three values of mean (7.8), mode (8.0) and median (8.0) of the EG are almost the same, and this allows the researcher to reach a conclusion that the EG individuals contributed their scores normally. Meanwhile, similar values of the CG are not the same; there exist two modes (7.0 and 8.5), which reveals that the scores got bimodal distribution. As seen above, there is a considerable gap between the two groups' means of scores on the listening

comprehension from post-test. On average, the EG learners achieved a 0.85 point higher than those of the CG did. And the results of *t*-test calculation reveals that the value *p* is smaller than the cutoff point of 0.05. This mean that the difference in these means is statistically significant. For this reason, it was safe to reject the null hypothesis of no difference in listening comprehension between the two groups.

This result indicates a positive trend towards improvement achieved by the EG learners, so the researcher can be confident to inferentially state that those students who studied English listening with pre-listening activities within the activation of background knowledge during ten weeks made a significant progress in the overall academic listening comprehension ability. While the students obtained such a result in their performance, how did they reflect on such a way of teaching with the teacher’s trialed method?

4.2 Students’ attitudes through two sets of questionnaires and interview

4.2.1 Learning English listening before the experiment

As presented in Table 3 below, before receiving the treatment, the student participants experienced different ways of learning listening comprehension from their former teacher(s), and here were 13 students choosing the answer “Yes” to this question “Did your former teacher(s) set any activities before playing CDs to help you better understand the listening?”, Therefore, 25 students in EG group must be divided into two small groups, one did not experience the pre-listening activities (Group 1) and the other were used to learning with these (Group 2).

Table 3: How students learned English listening with their former teacher(s)

No	Question (N = 25) – Listening comprehension taught by former teachers	F	%
1	Teacher set some activities before playing CDs.	13	52
2	Teacher explained new words and structures, and students listened and did exercises in their course-book.	16	64
3	Teacher played CDs several times without any explanation, and students listened and repeated.	8	32
4	Teacher played CDs, and students listened and followed the script.	5	20
5	Teacher played CDs, and students listened and answered the questions.	14	56
6	Students listened and summarized or said what they had heard in their ways.	5	20

4.2.2 Students' evaluations of listening learning before and after the experiment

Table 4: The attitudes of Group 1 and Group 2 before and after the experiment

Learning English listening before and after the treatment	Pre-Q		<i>t</i> value	<i>p</i>	Post-Q		<i>t</i> value	<i>p</i>
	Group 1	Group 2			Group 1	Group 2		
	Mean	Mean			Mean	Mean		
How Easy	4.3	3.4	2.61	0.015	2.0	2.15	0.67	0.509
How Enjoyable	4.0	2.5	3.99	0.001	2.08	2.46	1.42	0.169

The students' evaluations in terms of "easy" and "enjoyable" are found through question "What do you think about learning English listening with your former teacher(s)?" They were measured relying on five levels (1-5). The first item was arranged from "very easy" (1) to "very difficult" (5), and the second one was ranked from "very enjoyable" (1) to "very boring" (5). The results of such measurements from both pre- and post-questionnaires are summarized and shown in Table 4.

From pre-questionnaire results, we can realize that before the program was applied, the means for both items by Group 1 ($M_{\text{Easy}} = 4.33$ and $M_{\text{Enjoyable}} = 4.00$) are very high, much higher than the medium point of 3.0. That is the students of this group felt very difficult and very boring with the learning before the program. Meanwhile, those by Group 2 ($M_{\text{Easy}} = 3.46$ and $M_{\text{Enjoyable}} = 2.53$) fall into the points between 2.50 and 3.49; that means the learners of this group had no idea on the learning. When put in comparison, the means of both items of the two groups show differences. More convincingly, with the computation of an independent samples *t*-test, the mean difference of the first item is noticeable ($t = 2.61$, $df = 23$, $p = 0.015 < 0.05$). Similarly, the means of the second item were also proved to be significantly different ($t = 3.99$, $df = 23$, $p = 0.001 < 0.05$).

In short, before the intervention, those students who did not experience learning listening with pre-listening activities had negative attitudes towards the learning, while those who were accustomed to such a way of learning showed no judgment towards it.

However, the results of post-questionnaire show us very surprising differences. With a quick look at Table 5, we can see that the mean difference between the two questionnaires within each group indicates one more interesting thing. The distances in means showing the attitudes of Group 1 before and after the experiment are very big ($MD_{\text{Easy}} = 2.33$ and $MD_{\text{Enj}} = 1.92$), while those of Group 2 are also big for one item ($MD_{\text{Easy}} = 1.30$) but very small for the other ($MD_{\text{Enjoyable}} = 0.07$).

Table 5: The attitudes of Group 1 and Group 2 before and after the experiment

Learning English listening before and after the treatment	Group 1		Mean Difference (MD)	Group 2		Mean Difference (MD)
	Pre-Q	Post-Q		Pre-Q	Post-Q	
	Mean	Mean		Mean	Mean	
How Easy	4.33	2.00	2.33	3.4615	2.1538	1.30
How Enjoyable	4.0	2.08	1.92	2.5385	2.4615	0.07

In general, the students of two groups possessed the same positive attitudes after the treatment with the same method by the same teacher. Interestingly, there is much change in evaluations by Group 1 before and after the treatment, but not much by Group 2; that is the attitude of Group 1 students was much more affected by the program than that of Group 2 students. In fact, after receiving the treatment, the learners of Group 2 only appreciated the ease of the learning; they did not have the same evaluation on the joy of the learning. Such views by the students of two groups were carefully explained in their answers to the open-ended question on learning with pre-listening activities in the post-questionnaire.

4.2.3. Students' explanation for their evaluations

From the table 6 below, we can see that the majority of students of both groups attributed their interests in learning listening to the present teacher for her helpful activities, clear and careful explanation before listening, and interesting way of teaching. However, as observed in the table, half of Group 1 students (6/12) stated that "Teacher's interesting way of teaching" made them hold positive attitudes towards the pre-listening activities. Meanwhile, more than half of Group 2 students (7/13) had a good impression on such activities because of their helpfulness. The same quantity of the students in this group (7/13) stressed "Teacher's clear and careful explanations before listening" as the reasons that made them reach good evaluations above.

Table 6: Summary of explanations for students' reflections

No	Explanations for students' attitudes	The number of students		
		N = 25	G1 N=12	G2 N=13
1	Helpful activities for students to do before listening (discussion, questions, quizzes, prediction, brainstorming words, ideas, ...)	11	4	7
2	Teacher's clear and careful explanation before listening (key words and structures, hints, real life experience, setting, ...)	12	5	7

No	xplanations for students' attitudes	The number of students		
		N = 25	G1 N=12	G2 N=13
3	Teacher's interesting way of teaching	9	6	3
4	Teacher's good pronunciation	2	2	0
5	Teacher's enthusiasm	5	3	2

However, with a look at each group's responses, there is a little difference. More students of Group 1 highly appreciated the teacher's interesting way of teaching, which was preferred by 6/12 students than those of Group 2 (3/13 students). In fact, the number of students mentioning these reasons is also considerable (4/12 and 5/12, respectively). For example, one student explained that: "My teacher is very enthusiastic. Importantly, she always helps me and my classmates with different activities, such as providing some words related to what we are going to hear. This makes us easier to understand the listening". In addition, another student said: "My teacher has an interesting way of teaching, and she also extends her concern to every student, so most of us worked hard but felt happy".

Unlike Group 1, Group 2 with more students paid attention to the first two themes (7/13 students for each). For instance, one of them revealed: "My teacher offers clear explanations and illustrations related to the topic to be heard; this generates an exciting atmosphere in listening class"(S-14). Additionally, S-19 eagerly stated that the teacher gave them a lot of helpful activities before listening, such as providing some necessary new words, asking them to discuss in groups, having them predict the listening content and encouraging them to write down their own ideas.

Inferentially, the intervention, pre-listening activities to activate students' BK, by the researcher really creates a significant difference in their attitudes towards listening comprehension learning. One more issue of this section is an investigation into their attitudes towards the pre-listening activities employed before by their former teacher(s) and those done by the researcher.

4.2.4. Students' reflections on pre-listening activities to activate back ground knowledge

The students' reflections presented and analyzed in this part are the answers to two questions: "Which pre-listening activities do the students like?", and "What do they think about them?" When having a quick look at the data in Table 7, we can easily recognize that a large proportion of the students showed their favor for four activities: "Talking about the picture", "teacher explaining words, structures or/and concepts", "predicting content through questions", and "discussing personal experience concerning the topic". Moreover, the number of students of two groups voting for these pre-listening activities is almost similar. This does not mean they ignored the other two: "Doing True/False quizzes or ordering events probably occurring in the listening" and "brainstorming the words, structures and/or ideas about the topic".

Table 7: Students' preference for the pre-listening activities after the experiment

Pre-listening activities to activate background knowledge preferred and evaluated by students		Post-questionnaire					
		Group 1 (N=12)			Group 2 (N=13)		
		F	%	Rank	F	%	Rank
1	Talking with your classmates about the pictures in the book	9	75	2	10	76.9	2
2	Teacher explaining words, structures or/and concepts related to the topic	10	83.3	1	9	69.2	3
3	Predicting content of the listening through answering questions	9	75	2	11	84.6	1
4	Doing True/False quizzes or ordering events probably occurring in the listening	7	58.3	3	8	61.5	4
5	Discussing your personal experience or general knowledge concerning the topic with your classmates	9	75	2	10	76.9	2
6	Brainstorming the words, structures or/and ideas you know about the topic	6	50	4	7	53.8	5

In brief, after the teacher's application, six types of pre-listening activities to activate the students' background knowledge were proved to have nearly the same impression on the participant students of the two groups. However, while the largest quantity of Group 1 students liked the activity of explaining words, structures and concepts, that of Group 2 students preferred the one of predicting content through questions.

As analyzed above, the importance of the trialed pre-listening activities was quickly perceived by the students who had not accessed them earlier, and reasserted by those who had experienced such activities before learning listening with the researcher. Generally speaking, the innovative materials achieved a good impression on all the students of the research sample.

The use of pre-listening activities in exploiting the students' BK in teaching listening could not only improve their listening comprehension ability but also bring them positive attitudes towards the learning and teaching of the skill. Therefore, the following discussion will be the presentation of the achievements in their listening comprehension and those in their attitudes towards the reformed teaching, especially towards the activities applied.

2 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The experimental teaching was carried out based on a theoretical framework related to background knowledge, the use of this knowledge in language teaching and its implication for

pre-listening activities. Data collected before and after the course was analyzed and discussed in two preceding chapters.

After the trialed teaching, there are some notices made for the teaching of listening section in this course-book. The first notice for teachers in their listening teaching with this course-book is a careful preparation of pre-listening tasks for the listening section of each unit. The tasks need to focus on the aims to remind students of linguistic knowledge they learned and other types of background knowledge they experienced. The second suggestion for teachers is that they should not hesitate to invest some time in these tasks. In order to get this achievement, teachers have to make use of their preparation in combination with their art of teaching; that is they had to flexibly manage the situation each time they teach in classroom. Another important suggestion teachers should be aware of is that the exploitation of the background knowledge to serve the teaching and learning depends on the fruitful knowledge which they have saved long before, gathered when they prepare the tasks, or even aspired right at the time they teach the lesson in class. The last point to remind teachers is that they should not ask students to read the listening texts before having them listen because this is not an appropriate method of teaching listening, nor a way of assisting them to improve their listening comprehension.

In short, to enable students to engage themselves in learning listening and doing pre-listening tasks actively, teachers have to take a rather heavy role, investing both time and knowledge.

The researcher does expect that studies in the future will be done with a better attention paid to the methodology to produce even more reliable findings. Besides, she hopes that there will be further studies to investigate other innovative methods for the teaching of listening comprehension.

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APPENDIX

PRE-QUESTIONNAIRE

This questionnaire is part of a larger study aiming at exploring your attitudes towards learning English listening in general and learning this subject in classroom with your FORMER teacher(s) of English in particular. Please give your immediate feelings after reading each question. Your true feelings are very important for my study.

Please read the questions carefully and kindly put a tick (✓) in the box right beside the options indicating your choice.

SECTION A: Personal Information

1- Gender: male female

2- Age:

3- Hometown:

4- Number of years to study English: < 4 4 – 7 > 7

5- Email:

SECTION B: About the Learning of English Listening (put the tick in the box next to the number you choose)

1. Do you like learning English listening? 1.1 Yes 1.2 No

- If 'Yes', please point out your reason(s). (You may have more than one choice.)

1.1.1 Because it is necessary for my work and my life.

1.1.2 Because it is part of my favorite subject – English.

1.1.3 Because it is useful for my communication with foreigners.

1.1.4 Because it helps me enjoy English music.

1.1.5 Other reason(s):

2. Do you think learning English listening is difficult? 2.1 Yes 2.2 No

- If 'Yes', please point out your reason(s). (You may have more than one choice)

2.1.1 Because I am short of vocabulary.

2.1.2 Because it is hard to recognize the speaker's words.

2.1.3 Because it is not easy to find out to the main idea of the listening.

2.1.4 Because it is difficult to realize important details of the listening.

2.1.5 Other reason(s):

SECTION C: About the Teaching of English Listening (put the tick in the box next to the number you choose)

1. How were your English listening lessons taught before?

1.1 Teacher set some activities before playing the CDs.

1.2 Teacher explained new words and structures, and students listened and did the exercises in the book.

1.3 Teacher played the CDs several times without any explanation, and students listened and repeated.

1.4 Teacher played the CDs, and students listened and followed the script.

1.5 Teacher played the CDs, and students listened and answered teacher's questions.

1.6 Students summarized or told what they heard in their ways.

1.7 Other(s):

2. What do you think about learning English listening in question 3 above?

(put the tick in the box next to the number you choose)

2.1 Very easy Easy No idea Difficult Very difficult

2.2 Very enjoyable Enjoyable No idea Boring Very boring

SECTION D: About the Teaching of Listening with Pre-listening Activities (put the tick in the box next to the number you choose)

If your CHOSE of 1.1 for the question 1 of section C above is positive, you will choose 'yes' for the following question and continue to answer three more questions as below.

* Did your former teachers set any activities before playing the CDs to help you better understand the listening? Yes No

1. How often did your former teachers do so?

Always 1.2 Usually 1.3 Often 1.4 Sometimes 1.5 Rarely

2. Which of the following activities were you asked to do?

2.1 Talking with your classmates about the pictures in the book.

2.2 Predicting the content of the listening through answering questions, doing T/F quizzes.

2.3 Ordering events probably occurring in the listening.

2.4 Discussing your personal experience or general knowledge with your classmates.

2.5 Brainstorming all the words, structures or ideas you know about the topic.

2.6 Other(s):

3. What do you think about these activities? (circle the number)

3.1

Necessary 1 2 3 4. Unnecessary

3.2

Interesting 1 2 3 4. Uninteresting

Thank you for your cooperation!

POST- QUESTIONNAIRE

This questionnaire is part of a larger study aiming at exploring your attitudes towards learning English listening in general and learning this subject in classroom with your PRESENT teachers of English in particular. Please give your immediate feelings after reading each question. Your true feelings are very important for my study.

Please read the questions carefully and kindly put a tick (✓) in the box right beside the options indicating your choice.

SECTION A: Personal Information

1- Gender: male female

2- Age:

3- Hometown:

4- Number of years to study English: < 4 4 – 7 > 7

5- Email:

SECTION B: About The Learning of English Listening (put the tick in the box next to the number you choose)

1. Do you like learning English listening? 1.1 Yes 1.2 No

- If 'Yes', please point out your reason(s). (You may have more than one choice)

1.1.1 Because it is necessary for my work and my life.

1.1.2 Because it is part of my favorite subject – English.

1.1.3 Because it is useful for my communication with foreigners.

1.1.4 Because it helps me enjoy English music.

1.1.5 Other reason(s):

2. Do you think learning English listening is difficult? 2.1 Yes 2.2 No

- If 'Yes', please point out your reason(s). (You may have more than one choice)

2.1.1 Because I am short of vocabulary.

2.1.2 Because it is hard to recognize the speaker's words.

2.1.3 Because it is not easy to find out to the main idea of the listening.

2.1.4 Because it is difficult to realize important details of the listening.

2.1.5 Other reason(s):

SECTION C: About the Teaching English Listening with Pre-listening Activities (put the tick in the box next to the number you choose)

1. What do you think about learning English listening with your PRESENT teacher

1.1 Very easy Easy No idea Difficult Very difficult

1.2 Very enjoyable Enjoyable No idea Boring Very boring

2. What are the reasons that make you think so?

.....

SECTION D: About pre-listening activities

D.1. Which of the following PRE-LISTENING ACTIVITIES you like? (put the tick in the box next to the number you choose)	D.2. What do you think about these activities? (circle one of the numbers that best describes your reasons).
1.1 <input type="checkbox"/> Talking with your classmates about the pictures in the book.	2.1 -Necessary 1__ 2__ 3__ 4__ 5 Unnecessary. Interesting 1__ 2__ 3__ 4__ 5 Uninteresting.
1.2 <input type="checkbox"/> Getting topic-related words or/ and concepts explained by teacher.	2.2-Necessary 1__ 2__ 3__ 4__ 5 Unnecessary. - Interesting 1__ 2__ 3__ 4__ 5 Uninteresting.
1.3 <input type="checkbox"/> Predicting the content of the listening through answering questions.	2.3 -Necessary 1__ 2__ 3__ 4__ 5 Unnecessary. - Interesting 1__ 2__ 3__ 4__ 5 Uninteresting.

1.4 <input type="checkbox"/> Ordering events probably occurring in the listening and/or doing T/F quizzes.	2.4-Necessary 1__2__3__4__5 Unnecessary. -Interesting 1__2__3__4__5 Uninteresting.
1.5 <input type="checkbox"/> Discussing your personal experience or general knowledge concerning the topic with your classmates.	2.5-Necessary 1__2__3__4__5 Unnecessary. -Interesting 1__2__3__4__5 Uninteresting.
1.6 <input type="checkbox"/> Brainstorming all the words, structures or ideas you know about the topic.	2.6-Necessary 1__2__3__4__5 Unnecessary. -Interesting 1__2__3__4__5 Uninteresting.

SECTION E: About the students' difficulties

1. What are your difficulties when you learn English listening with your PRESENT teacher?

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Thank you for your cooperation!

RESULTS OF TESTS FROM THE EXPERIMENTAL GROUP AND CONTROL GROUP

No	THE EXPERIMENTAL GROUP		THE CONTROL GROUP	
	PRE-TEST	POST-TEST	PRE-TEST	POST-TEST
1	8.0	8.0	4.0	6.0
2	8.0	8.0	4.5	7.5
3	5.0	8.5	9.0	8.5
4	6.5	8.5	6.5	4.0
5	6.0	8.0	6.5	5.5
6	6.0	8.0	6.0	6.5
7	6.0	7.0	5.0	8.0
8	5.5	6.0	6.5	7.0
9	5.0	7.0	5.5	5.5
10	4.0	8.0	6.0	8.5
11.	7.0	9.0	8.5	9.0
12.	5.0	8.0	5.0	8.5
13	6.5	8.0	6.5	6.5
14	6.0	7.0	6.5	7.0
15	6.5	8.0	5.0	7.0
16	7.5	8.0	6.5	7.5
17	7.5	8.5	8.0	9.0
18			4.5	4.0